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Press and Punjabi Suba Movement (1950-1966)

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Abstract

After a prolonged political battle, the Akali Dal succeeded in securing the formation of a separate state in 1966, which allowed Punjabis to preserve their language and culture. However, this achievement came after a lengthy and challenging struggle. In 1956, following the States Reorganisation Act, PEPSU was merged into Punjab, which set the stage for the Punjabi Suba movement to gain renewed momentum in its quest for a separate state. During this period, the press played a pivotal role in documenting the movement, covering the key actions and decisions of its prominent leaders, and ensuring the public stayed informed about the ongoing efforts toward realizing the goal of a distinct Punjabi state.

Keywords Punjabi Suba, Punjab, Akali Dal etc.

Introduction

Based on the Punjabi Suba, the Akali Dal decided to run in the 1952 election. Three parties ran in the election: the Communists, the Akalis, and the Pepsu Congress, led by Col. Raghbir Singh. In this election, the Congress severely outperformed the Akali Dal in both Punjab and Pepsu. Just 33 of the 186 legislative seats were won by the Akali Dal. There was little appeal to the Congress. The Akali Dal was unable to prove that they were safe representatives of the Sikhs and did not garner the backing they had hoped for. Six seats were gained by the Communists.[1] The Congress even got more votes than the Akali in two Sikh majority districts, Amritsar and Patiala. However in Pepsu, Akalis succeeded in forming a United Front Ministry comprising anti-Congress elements such as Col. Raghbir's party and independents led by Gian Singh Rarewala.[2]

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to discuss about the Press and Punjabi Suba Movement (1950-1966)

Review of Literature

On 21 April 1952, the non-Congress ministry with Rarewala as its head was formed with the help of the legislators from the Hindi speaking Zone.[3] In 1952, the United Front Ministry appointed another Committee of seven members of the Assembly headed by Sardar Dara Singh; M.L.A. and other members were Pritam Singh Sidhu, Bachan Singh, Gurdial Singh, Sunder Singh, Sampuran Singh.[4] In December 1952,

Master Tara Singh demanded the creation of a Punjabi speaking State by taking certain portions of Punjab and Pepsu in forming them into one administration unit. While asking for the amalgamation of Pepsu and Punjabi-speaking region to constitute a Punjabi Suba, At this point, they were certain that the state would inevitably have a Sikh majority. In a July 1953 decision, the Akali Dal Working Committee declared that the Sikhs had not benefited from the country's freedom. In every aspect of life, they have been specifically

singled out for discrimination. They have tried every constitutional and nonviolent way to resolve the issues, but they haven't even been given a hearing.[5]

Although the Rarewala cabinet was in power for roughly a year, overly ambitious lawmakers, especially those from the Hindi-speaking section of the Union, constantly threatened to desert. Faction conflicts among the Akalis and the Communist M.L.As' conditional support hindered the Rarewala Ministry's ability to operate effectively. A period of perplexing political circumstances culminated in Rarewala's ministry's resignation on March 1, 1953. Sampuran Singh Raman and Pritam Singh Gojran formed two factions inside the Pepsu Akali Dal. On March 25, 1953, Pritam Singh Gojran was chosen as the Riasti Akali Dal's president.[6]

The Lok Sabha approved the establishment of President Rule in Pepsu on 12 March 1953. The Rajya Sabha approved it on 26 March 1953. In the following some significant changes were witnessed in the behavior pattern and character of the political parties.[7] The Pepsu Congressmen wanted Pepsu to be merged into Punjab but the Punjab Congressmen opposed this proposal as they apprehended that it would involve the surrender of their Hind speaking areas where they had the maximum mass appeal.[8] The Akali Dal in Pepsu was prepared to surrender the Hindi speaking areas of Narnaul and Kandaghat. If the Ganganagar district of Rajsthan could be transferred to Pepsu. This, the Akali Dal in Pepsu pleaded would ensure a Sikh majority State, continuance of a Sikh Rajpramukh and it would provide a homeland for the Khalsa. The political crises in Pepsu and imposition of President rule spurred the Akali Dal for greater tempo in demanding Punjabi Suba.[9]

On December 29, 1953, the States Reorganisation Commission was established by the Parliament. Its members were: (i) Orissa Governor Saiyed Fazl Ali, who served as its chairman; (ii) Hariday Nath Kunzru, a member of the Council of States; and (iii) Kavalam Madhava Pannikar, the Indian ambassador to Egypt. "Investigate the conditions of the problem, the historical background, the existing situation, and the bearing of all important and relevant factors thereon," was the mandate given to the Commission. On February 23, 1954, the Commission requested written memoranda from associations and members of the public.[10]

In light of this, it received 155250 documents; however, the Commission only chose 2000 well crafted memos for its review. Nine thousand people, including representatives of political parties, public associations, social workers, journalists, and municipal and district boards, were interviewed by the Commission throughout its nationwide trip. The Punjabi Suba problem was the main reason the Akali Dal ran in the 1954 Pepsu poll. With Brish Bhan serving as his deputy and Col. Raghbir Singh as premier, the Congress took power in Pepsu.[11]

The right-wing Pepsu Akali Dal opposed Pepsu's merger with Punjab and supported the company's continued existence. They believed that the Sikhs would not benefit from Pepsu's unification with Punjab. The Sikh majority in Pepsu is merely marginal, making up little over 49% of the population and outnumbering Hindus by just 20,000. Pritam Singh Gojran voiced his disapproval of Pepsu's expansion.[12]

Main Text

The leftist wing of the Riasti Akali Dal (Raman group) stood for the merger of the Punjabi speaking areas of Pepsu with the Punjab. The leftist wing of Riasti Akali Dal rejected the demand for Greater Punjab.[13] The Pepsu Government considered the sponsors of the Maha Punjab move as 'communalists'. Their plea for a bigger unit on the border from the view-point of strategic considerations were countered by the argument that the smaller units were more convenient for defence purposes.[14] In November 1954, Chief Minister Col. Raghbir Singh strongly pleaded for retention of Pepsu as a separate State.[15] The picture was radically changed after the death of Raghbir Singh. Soon after Brish Bhan's taking over as Chief Minister of Pepsu a piquant situation arose because he was known to have pro-merger view which ran counter to the stand taken by the Pepsu Government in the memorandum submitted to the State Reorganisation Commission.[16] The Pepsu Government appointed a Committee of eighteen members under the Chairmanship of Ram Saran Mittal, Pepsu Assembly Speaker, to advise it on the problem of reorganization of the State.[17]

In addition to Jagan Nath Kaushal, Gian Singh Rarewala, Gojran, and Ranjit Singh representing the United Front and Akali Dal, the Congress members of the Committee included the Raja of Nalagarh, Hansraj Sharma (Phagwara), and Major Amir Singh, who represented the three enclaves of Kandaghat, Kapurthala, and Mahendergarh. Albel Singh served as the Sampuran Singh Raman group's Sanjha Morcha secretary. The three public figures, Gurdial Singh Dhillon, Lachman Das, and Seth Joti Parsad, were all Patiala Congressmen.[18] Gian Singh Rarewala as could be understood subscribed to the

above school of thought, supporting the demand of a Punjabi speaking State in the firm of a modified Pepsu. He recommended that the historical background and tradition of this region would help to retain the Pepsu in its modified form. He expressed the opinion that even after Kapurthala, Mahendergarh, Kandaghat areas were taken away from Pepsu, the State would remain a viable unit.

But to make it stronger and self sufficient, he suggested that the contiguous Punjabi - speaking areas of Punjab be incorporated into Pepsu.[19] The Advisory Committee considered the demand of Punjabi speaking State to be a communal demand, reciprocally, the demand for a Maha Punjab was considered to have been actuated by a desire to create a very big State so that the Sikhs may be reduced to a negligible minority.[20] Pritam Singh Gojran, Pepsu Akali Chief and a member of the Advisory Committee was in the favour of Greater Pepsu. He wanted that Hindi speaking areas should be cut off from Pepsu while the Punjabi speaking areas of Punjab and Ganganagar in Rajasthan should be integrated with it.[21] The Advisory Committee recommended the formation of Maha Punjab by the merger of Pepsu, Punjab and Himachal Pradesh. The demand as such was made on historical, cultural and defence grounds.[22] The Punjab States Committee, which had been formed at the Leftist Parties Convention for the formation of the Punjabi speaking State in October 1953. The Committee demanded the disintegration of Pepsu and Punjab States so that the Punjabi speaking contiguous Zones of the two Stats could be merged with a view to unifying all the Punjabi speaking areas into one State.[23]

On April 18, 1955, nearly every political party and other group met with the States Reorganization Commission. The Pepsu Akali Dal argued in favor of keeping Pepsu, ideally in a redesigned or expanded form. Three organizations—the Central Purushartha Sabha, the Krishak Samiti, and the Arya Smaj of Pepsu—demanded that Pepsu unite with Punjab and Himachal.[24] Representatives of traders and Aija Samajists demanded the formation of Maha Punjab. The Pepsu branch of the Bhartiya Jan Sangh, the Hindu Mahasabha and the Rashtriya Swayam Sewak Sangh reiterated their demand for Maha Punjab. The Praja Socialist Party made a case for the redistribution of the northern Indian region into States on a linguistic and cultural basis.[25] In the second half of 1954 the Punjab was full of excitement generated by almost a public debate on the respective merits of the Punjabi Suba and the Maha Punjab. While the Reorganisation Commission was touring the rest of the country, the Akalis in the Punjab were relying support for Punjabi Suba and the Punjab Congress holding public meetings against this demand and mobilising support for the Maha Punjab. The climax was reached on the eve of elections for the Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee to be held in January 1955.[26]

The Akali Dal extened this election contests on the issue of Punjabi Suba in alliance with the Desh Bhagat Board of the Communist. The Akali Dal won an overwhelming majority of the seats. The Congress sponsored Khalsa Dal, had contested 132 seats and won only 3 seats.[27] The Sikh public opinion was being mobilised in favour of Punjabi Suba in order to curb the rising demand, the Sachar Ministry imposed a ban of the Punjabi suba slogan, on the plea that it was endangering communal harmony in the State. During an interview Bhim Sen Sachar (the Chief Minister of Punjab) on 21 January 1955 said,

'Master Tara Singh stated that he did not believe in a linguistic Punjabi State. What he had in a mind, was a Sikh State where the Sikhs would be in a numerical majority.[28]

On May 10, 1955, Master Tara Singh made the decision to launch Morcha. On July 12, 1955, the administration lifted the prohibition order after realizing how serious the situation was. The Akalis put a stop to their sixty-four-day-old morcha, but the Akali agitation continued into a new phase once the State Reorganisation Commission's report was released. On September 30, 1955, the States Reorganisation Commission issued its recommendations after taking into account a number of petitions and initiatives. The Commission argued in its report that Pepsu was geographically and physically a part of Punjab. From the point of view of population Pepsu was the smallest of the part B States. The demand of its merger as a whole or by parts in the adjoining areas had been voiced by the political parties right from the time of its formation tilt the appointment of States Reorganisation Commission. The Commission argued that Pepsu was an artificial unit and could not continue under any scheme of reorganisation.[29]

The Commission stated: "We believe that even with its current territory, the State cannot be considered a sizable unit, and it will become extremely difficult for this State to maintain its separate existence with the merger of outlying pockets in the adjoining areas, which should follow as a natural corollary of territorial readjustment in this area." The report of the States Reorganisation Commission was extensively debated in state legislatures, parliament, and other political forums. Reactions to it were varied. While most Hindus were happy, it caused violent outbursts in Sikh communities. The Akalis felt perturbed over the report. They had hoped that the middle way could be found between

the two extreme demands of Maha Punjab and Punjabi Suba. Master Tara Singh denounced the report as a decree of Sikh annihilation.[30]

The Akali Party in Punjab showed complete indifference to the Pepsu's retention. Master Tara Singh said that he would continue his struggle for Punjabi Suba even if Pepsu was retained. The Akalis from Pepsu tried to persuade Master Tara Singh to accept retention of Pepsu as a temporary alternative to the Punjabi Suba demand. The States Reorganisation Commission had made out a well reasoned case that Pepsu was not a viable unit. The Congress Party viewed the recommendations of the States Reorganisation Commission favourably and managed a unanimous resolution. It hailed the liquidation of Pepsu, pleaded for the recognition of Patiala and expressed satisfaction over the abolition of the institution of Rajpramukh. Consequently the institution of the Rajpramukh was abolished. In the Pepsu it was felt that Patiala should be made the capital of the new Punjab State. The demand of making Patiala the capital of the new State was voiced by the majority of the members in the Punjab Vidhan Sabha.[31]

The Akali Dal ended its agitation, negotiations were held between the Central government leaders and several Akali leadrs. Master Tara Singh met Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru on 24 October 1955 in the presence of Abdul Kamal Kalam Azad and G.B. Panth.[32] Meanwhile the States Reorganisation Commission recommended the merger of Punjab, absolutely unacceptable to the Akali Dal. Eventually, a compromise solution - later known as the Regional Formula was reached. Master Tara Singh was accompanied by Giani Kartar Singh, Hukam Singh, Gian Singh Rarewala and Bhai Jodh Singh. Their talks were inconclusive. Another deputation met the Prime Minister to suggest that the Pepsu formula could be extended to the Punjab for solving the language problem and Punjabi language could be promoted in the whole State.[33]

Hukam Singh had formulated a scheme which essentially met some of the Akali demands without actually creating a Punjabi - speaking State. This becomes the basis of discussion in January 1956.[34] On 11 March 1956, the general body meeting of the Akali Dal was held, Gian Singh Rarewala presented the Regional Formula and Giani Kartar Singh supported it.

In this time Master Tara Singh said, 'our object is not to create trouble. The proposal offered by the government does not constitute the Punjabi Suba but under the present circumstances, I do not want to fight.'[35]

The Regional Formula divided the State into two regions namely Punjabi speaking and Hindi speaking regions. Under the regional formula the State of Pepsu was merged in the Punjab in 1956. The formula provided that the provisions of the Sachar Formula concerning the medium of instruction would continue to apply in the areas of the Punjab before the merger and that in the areas of the former Pepsu State the arrangement already existing therein regarding language instruction would continue. The Akali Party was in a situation of political drift and Gian Singh Rarewala even said in statement that under the changed circumstances, the Akali Dal should leave the political field continue itself only to the social, cultural, religious and educational activities of the Sikhs and allow its members and supporters to join the national and progressive forces.[36]

The Raman group rejected the proposal to establish Patiala as the capital of the new state of Chandigarh. The Chandigarh Capital Project administrator rejected Patiala's proposal. Although the final result did not favor Patiala City, it was agreed to keep some significant government offices in Patiala in line with the States Reorganisation Commission's recommendations. To make it easier for his organization to join the Congress, Gian Singh Rarewala even initiated conversations with the Congress leaders. Because he believed that the Sikhs were an autonomous political body, Master Tara Singh swiftly denounced Rarewala's action as treason and stated that the Akali Dal will continue to exist independently.[37]

Rarewala's recommendation to join the Congress Party was described by Hukam Singh as "virtually an act of sabotage" and a betrayal of confidence. Rarewala and his five colleagues were even ejected by the Working Committee for their lobbying. Nevertheless, the Akali Dal began discussing political cooperation with Congress officials due to the growing support for the Congress among Sikhs in rural areas.[38] The States Reorganisation Commission recommended the integration of Punjab, Pepsu and Himachal Pradesh into the administrative unit. On 1 November 1956, Pepsu became part of the larger State of the Punjab.[39] The Congress High Command was blamed for giving encouragement to Sardar Partap Singh Kairon to subdue the Akalis. In the same month, in a big Akali conference held at Batala on 13 July 1958, Master Tara Singh repeated all these charges and emphasized that the Sikhs were in a danger from the Hindu majority and the Congress government.[40] Master Tara Singh severally attacked Giani Kartar

Singh and clubbed him as 'a traitor of the Sikh community'. [41] Sardar Hukam Singh, the Deputy Speaker of Lok Sabha supported Giani Kartar Singh. Giani Kartar Singh charged Master Tara Singh that his leadership was in danger and not the Sikhs. Giani Kartar Singh supported Prem Singh Lalpura against Master Tara Singh. Master Tara Singh was defeated by three votes because of Giani Kartar Singh got the support of all the 24 Communist members and three Congress member in the election of Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee Master Tara Singh revived the agitation and was arrested. [42]

On December 18, 1960, Sant Fateh Singh began a death fast while Master Tara Singh was incarcerated. Sant Fateh Singh was convinced that the Prime Minister had changed his mind and was prepared to engage in negotiations by Master Tara Singh, who had been freed by the government in the interim. After that, Sant Fateh Singh had multiple meetings with the prime minister. These meetings produced no results. "After the failure of Nehru Fateh Singh talks, Master Tara Singh declared that the struggle for the creation of Punjabi Suba would continue." The Tribune's article under the captain, "No Direct Struggle," states that the Working Committees of the Akali Dal would decide what form that struggle would take. [43]

On August 15, 1961, Master Tara Singh began his 48-day fast until death. The promise that the Indian government would constitute a high-level Commission to investigate the allegations of discrimination against Sikhs was broken when the Commission was established on October 31, 1961. In its report from January 1962, the Commission concluded that the Punjabi Suba had a disguise for the demand for a Sikh State and found no evidence of prejudice against Sikhs. In 1962, Sant Fateh Singh established a rival Akali Dal to challenge Master Tara Singh's. Jawaharlal Nehru passed away on May 27, 1964, and the Das Commission forced Partap Singh Kairon to leave his position on June 14 of the same year.

Master Tara Singh incited Sant Fateh Singh to raise the issue of the Punjab Suba's establishment following his failure urged the January 1965 election for the Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee. Master Tara Singh advocated for "a self determined status for the Sikhs within the Union of India" in his statement dated August 2, 1965. In response, the Sant group issued a resolution on August 5, 1965, restating its demand for the Punjabi-speaking States on a solely linguistic basis. [44]

Sant Fateh Singh issued an ultimatum on August 17, 1965, stating that if the Punjabi-speaking state was not founded within 25 days, he would begin a fast till death (that is, on September 10). If he survived for 15 days, he would then choose to burn himself on the 16th day. The Punjabi Suba controversy caused rifts among the Sikh authorities. While other Sikh MLAs distanced themselves from this stance, some fifteen Congress MLAs convened to press the administration to grant the Punjabi Suba demand; in the meantime, India and Pakistan went to war in 1965. Additionally, Gulzari Lai Nanda, the Union Home Minister, declared that the entire matter might be reexamined. Finally, Sant Fateh Singh withdrew his threat of setting himself on fire. [45]

The Home Minister declared in Parliament that the issue of Punjab's reorganization would be resolved by forming a Parliamentary Committee and a Cabinet Committee with Y.B. Chavan, the Defense Minister, Mrs. Indira Gandhi, the Information and Broadcasting Minister, and Mahavir Tyagi, the Rehabilitation Minister. When Lai Bahadur Shastri passed away in Tashkent on January 11, 1966, after traveling there to negotiate a peace accord with Pakistan under passion auspices, the Cabinet Committee took a different turn, with Mrs. Gandhi taking over as prime minister. Here, she indicated her preference for the creation of Punjabi Suba. Despite these accusations, Prime Minister Indira Gandhi managed to get a resolution passed in favor of the Punjabi-speaking state at a meeting of the Congress Working Committees without waiting for the Cabinet and Consultative Committees to report. On November 1, 1966, the State was restructured according to linguistic principles. [46]

Conclusion

The Punjabi Suba Movement was a significant chapter in the history of Punjab, driven by the desire to create a separate state where the Punjabi language and culture could thrive. The movement, which gained momentum after the merger of PEPSU into Punjab in 1956, was marked by the tireless efforts of political leaders, particularly the Akali Dal, who championed the cause of a Punjabi-speaking state. The struggle was long and arduous, involving multiple phases of political negotiation, protests, and public mobilization. One of the most important factors in the success of the Punjabi Suba Movement was the role of the press. The media acted as a bridge between the movement's leaders and the general public, keeping citizens informed about the progress and setbacks. Newspapers and journalists not only reported on the key events but also shaped public opinion and rallied support for the cause. They highlighted the cultural and

linguistic importance of creating a separate state for Punjabis and played a crucial role in galvanizing public sentiment. In conclusion, the Punjabi Suba Movement was not only a political struggle but also a cultural one, aiming to preserve the distinct identity of Punjabis. The press played an instrumental role in amplifying the movement's message, documenting its journey, and ensuring that the voices of its leaders and supporters were heard. Without the press's active involvement, it would have been difficult to generate the widespread awareness and support that ultimately led to the formation of Punjab as a separate state in 1966.

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